

Small and medium enterprises securing future-proof bioenergy chains

Summary Report

Europe's solid biomass to energy sector is dominated by SMEs. What is and can be their role in fostering innovation and growth in rural areas in view of the emerging bio-based circular economy?

The SecureChain project demonstrated how market uptake of efficient bioenergy systems and sustainable biomass mobilisation by SMEs can be promoted with the help of a dedicated innovation mentoring approach.

1. Context and objectives

Bioenergy refers to clean energy produced from a range of different renewable biomass feedstocks, of which a major share is wood / solid biomass. Bioenergy accounts for 61% of renewable energy consumption and 10% of the total energy mix in the EU-28 in 2015. The sector shows an average annual growth rate of 4.83% (2000-2015). Solid biomass clearly appears as the main source of fuel consumed, representing 95.3 Mtoe or 70% of the total 136.2 Mtoe inland energy consumption in 2015. In this context, it is clear that bioenergy will continue to play an important role in reaching the EU's 2030 and 2050 climate and energy objectives¹.

SecureChain was a Horizon 2020 project co-financed by the European Commission from 2015 to 2018, which focused on promoting market uptake of bioenergy in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The main objective was to promote a *Sustainable Supply Chain Management* practice that meets highest environmental quality and financial viability standards and targets local biomass suppliers, energy producers and financial sector players. Unique features of the project were that the entire bioenergy chain was considered, and sustainability and financing were an integral part of the project set-up. The specific objectives included the following:

The consortium of ten organisations united excellent competence in biomass, energy systems and efficiency, sustainability, certification and green investment (see list of partners on back cover). The project targeted SMEs in six model regions around Europe (see map), where it connected to various stakeholders in the bioenergy chain: energy agencies, cluster organisations, research centres, SMEs and industry associations.

¹ Figures based on AEBIOM Statistical Report 2017, www.aebiom.org

2. A mentoring approach for SMEs in bioenergy

Europe's solid biomass to energy sector is dominated by SMEs. What is and can be their role in fostering innovation and growth in rural areas in view of the emerging bio-based circular economy? SecureChain promoted the role of SMEs in bioenergy through a dedicated innovation mentoring package. Key activities included:

- **Innovation vouchers.** In an open contest, SMEs could apply for specific support of their own proposed pilot projects. The best SME pilot projects were selected and received hands-on technical advice from the project team.
- **Regional Lead Partners** were the main contact point for SMEs and ensured region-specific oversight and quality control of the pilots' implementation.
- **Learning Labs** and various trainings were offered to raise capabilities of SME owners and to ensure wider stakeholder engagement in the regions.
- **Sustainability checks.** *Life Cycle Assessments* (LCA) were carried out to evaluate the environmental impacts of SME pilots. Trainings and pre-checks helped SMEs to prepare successfully for *certification*.
- **Financial risk assessment** and advisory services to SMEs facilitated strategic business decisions and new investments into facilities and equipment.

3. Innovation vouchers and advisory support for local pilot projects

To stimulate engagement from local SMEs, an open call for promising pilot project ideas was launched simultaneously in all model regions. The scope of the call was - on purpose - broad and open to all SMEs in bioenergy, without any preference for a given fuel type or conversion technology. The pilot project idea, however, had to show good potential to foster biomass mobilisation and/or market uptake of efficient bioenergy systems. The call was opened in June 2016 for four months.

Following a thorough evaluation, all proposals were ranked according to six criteria, and the most suitable proposals were selected (20 out of 40 submitted proposals). These SMEs then engaged into a 2-years collaboration with the SecureChain team, coordinated and guided by the Regional Lead Partners.

The award of an innovation voucher of 3,000-5,000 € entitled an SMEs to obtain specific, dedicated advice from a local consultant of their choice, to support the development of the proposed solution and their business plan. Furthermore, the SMEs benefitted from the expertise of the consortium, which offered tailored advice and support for each individual pilot. The advisory services provided to SMEs through the vouchers and the consortium's work included:

- Assessment/mapping of locally available biomass supplies
- Technical appraisal and testing of new or improved equipment
- Feasibility of specific supply chain configurations and logistics
- Life Cycle Assessments of greenhouse gas emissions
- Cost-benefit analyses and exploitation calculations
- Financial risk analyses, investment scenarios, business plans
- Certification trainings and company pre-checks
- Trainings e.g. on biomass harvesting, quality and business plan development

SecureChain developed and tested this approach within a variety of companies and regional settings. The successful results show the potential of this method as a recommendable, transferable practice for support of market uptake by SMEs.

4. Supply chain canvas

The pilot projects cover the entire bioenergy chain, from biomass harvesting and fuel production to energy conversion and recycling. In all regions at least 3 pilot projects were initiated, ensuring an appropriate geographical coverage. The topics reflect the variety of technical solutions proposed by SMEs in the open contest.

<i>Biomass → Energy Supply Chains</i>	<i>Biomass harvesting</i> 			
<i>Region</i>				
Småland , Sweden (4 pilots)	Efficient harvesting of forest residues		Optimal biomass boilers for small municipalities	Wood ash pellets fertilizer
NRW , Germany * (3 pilots)	Improve biomass collection/sorting in trade centres	Valorise wood industry residues into pellets		
Gelderland & Overijssel , Netherlands (3 pilots)	Low-impact harvesting in landscape maintenance	Strategic storage facilities for quality wood chips		
Catalonia , Spain (4 pilots)	Optimise biomass logistics and trade centres	Up-scaling wood chips and pellet production	Renovated heating systems, cogeneration	
Western Macedonia , Greece (3 p.)	Fast growing tree plantations; mixed feedstocks	Wood wastes for energy use in wood industries	Improved biogas plant	
Southern Estonia (3 pilots)			Small CHP plants for village communities	Wood ash fertilizer production
Total: 20 pilots	8	4	6	2

5. Highlights of successful pilot projects

The following are good examples of successful collaborations of consortium partners with regional SMEs, consultants and public stakeholders, to develop, test and implement pilot project ideas of SME owners. See further details on the *Factsheets*.

- **Värnamo Energi AB**, Sweden. Biomass mobilisation through conversion of municipal heat plants. 14 small oil boilers in four villages are being replaced by four new biomass systems and an expansion and renewal of the district heating grid. The pilot investigated the optimal technical solution to supply heat to these communities and the interest of the potential local customers.
- **Lessebo Fjärrvärme**, Sweden. Exclude fossil fuel from the energy mix. A municipal heat plant company invested in an innovative flue gas condenser to ensure peak loads could be managed using bioenergy. The pilot will lead to expanded business and decreased emissions in the grid which supplies four communities.
- **Novalia Sinergie**, Catalonia, Spain. Upscaling of pellet production. The company enlarged their production by adding an extra pellet line for industrial pellets. The pilot was used to develop a commercial strategy and secure the funding for the enlargement. Furthermore, they obtained a certification for the domestic pellets.
- **AVEA GmbH & Co. KG**, Germany. Improved wood recovery from green wastes. A communal waste management company improved its green waste sorting process to make the underutilised wooden fraction accessible for thermal utilisation. The pilot helped to enlarge the capacity of the biomass yard and reduced greenhouse gas emissions per ton of green waste significantly.
- **Bruins & Kwast Biomass Management**, The Netherlands. Biomass mobilisation from landscape elements. The pilot included two companies, a municipality and a landscape management organisation, which aimed to select the optimal method for maintenance of a traditional cultural landscape with high ecological value. The pilot proved the feasibility under certain conditions and will be pursued in a follow-up demonstration project.

6. Learning Labs, stakeholder engagement and evaluation of results

Photo impressions from SecureChain Learning Labs and trainings

To ensure participation of more SMEs and other market actors, the project organised a series of regional outreach activities. The *Learning Labs* included meetings and workshops to sensitize local stakeholders about sustainable biomass use and bioenergy. SME owners presented their pilot projects together, allowing for regular feedback on the progress and impulses from other SMEs, experts and stakeholders.

Other participative events involved training sessions to raise capabilities of market actors, company visits, B2B seminars, presentations at industry fairs and conferences, and roundtables with public authorities and decision-makers. During study trips to other countries (Germany, Sweden, Austria), participants could visit various bioenergy companies and learn about best practice and latest systems (benchmarking).

An ex-post evaluation of the SMEs' experience showed significant appreciation, especially of the networking activities. 70% of SME pilot project owners indicated that they had taken concrete actions based on their involvement in SecureChain.

SMART performance criteria were assessed to measure the impact of each pilot at the end of the project. Substantial results were achieved (sum over all pilots, June 2018):

- Volume of additionally mobilised biomass: 142,000 tons/year
- Final renewable energy production: 2,300,000 GJ/year
- Reduced GHG emissions: 40,100 tons CO₂ eq./year
- Direct and indirect jobs created: 90 FTE/year
- Total investments triggered: 10.2 million EUR

7. Lessons learnt and main conclusions

Sustainable bioenergy projects are challenging for SMEs, because various business and environmental aspects along the whole supply chain play a role. Not every pilot project is a success story, but it increases the knowledge of the pilot owner and the involved stakeholders. SecureChain's experimental test of the practical mentoring scheme for SMEs led to the following main conclusions.

1. A **hands-on mentoring approach**, using a combination of innovation tools such as vouchers, technical and financial advisors, trainings, LCA and certification can effectively support SMEs to overcome their specific challenges and unlock the market uptake potential of bioenergy. These tools work best when they are delivered by well-established local consultants or agencies.
2. **Business clusters** can play a key role in boosting bioenergy by matching partners both in the supply and the innovation chain. SME members can benefit a lot from knowledge exchange, technical advice and business matchmaking offered by clusters, plus a greater visibility as a result of joint promotion. Clusters should however be bottom-up and steered by the SMEs' own interest.
3. **Public acceptance of bioenergy** is extremely important. Education and communication of the economic and ecological benefits towards the public, and within the bioenergy sector, are key. Projects should adhere to all relevant environmental legislation.
4. **Communicating best practice** of successful bioenergy projects even from other EU regions raises awareness and is a great trigger for market uptake. Lessons learnt from successful, and unsuccessful projects, should be disseminated and exploited much wider in the EU, in national languages, aimed specifically at SMEs.
5. The **multi-actor approach**, which aims at scientists and practitioners working together on real problems, is challenging for SMEs who have their mind focused on the daily operation. Good, continuous facilitation and tangible results are needed to make it work. Regional cultures and legal contexts have to be taken into account in the design of participative processes.

8. Pilot project factsheets

1. **Värnamo Energi AB**, Sweden. Biomass mobilisation through conversion of municipal heat plants.
2. **Lessebo Fjärrvärme**, Sweden. Exclude fossil fuel from the energy mix.
3. **Skogsbränsle Småland**, Sweden. Biomass mobilisation through ash recycling.
4. **AVEA GmbH & Co. KG**, Germany. Improved wood recovery from green wastes.
5. **Bruins & Kwast Biomass Management**, The Netherlands. Biomass mobilisation through landscape elements maintenance in Twente.
6. **RiBo Holding**, The Netherlands. Strategic Biomass Storage Facilities Gelderse Vallei
7. **Hissink & ZN**, The Netherlands. Innovative biomass harvesting machine for top-and branch wood.
8. **Novalia Sinergie**, Catalonia, Spain. Growing the production of modern solid biofuels for small-scale heaters.
9. **Sala Forestal SL**, Catalonia, Spain. Biomass distribution to end consumers with an innovative logistics model.
10. **Taarapõllu Talu OÜ**, Estonia. Small-scale CHP for autarky farms.
11. **Haldusühistu Ilmasaare MTÜ**, Estonia. Small-scale CHP wood gasifier for village cooperative.
12. **Alfa Wood Group**, Greece. More bark for biofuel, more wood for MDF!
13. **AZ Bioenergia**, Greece. Fast-growing biomass plantations for bioenergy end users.
14. **Matesion Ltd.**, Greece. Improving feedstock supply management in a local biogas plant in Kozani.
15. **Probiomassa**, Catalonia, Spain. Pellet production vs distribution, and full customer service (ESCO model).

Biomass mobilisation through conversion of heat plants

Project partners

Värnamo Energi AB

Värnamo Energi AB
Box 2268
S-331 02 Värnamo
Sweden
www.varnamoenergi.se

Finnvedsbostäder

Finnvedsbostäder
Box 446
S-331 24 Värnamo
Sweden
www.finnvedsbostader.se

Figure in the head: The plant in the city of Värnamo: Source: Värnamo Energi

The municipality of Värnamo and the company Finnvedsbostäder had several small local fossil fuelled boilers in various communities nearby the city. Several were in need of renovation, partly due to age but also to convert to more environmentally friendly fuels. Meanwhile, the municipality and the company perceived these units as relatively small and not their core business. As the small heat plants were in need of major renovation, a golden opportunity arose to capitalize on the synergies that can exist between the municipality, Finnvedsbostäder and the heat plants of Värnamo Energi, and also with external real estate owners. The Parties agreed that Värnamo Energi has the best conditions to realize such coordination for synergies. The company aims to meet a certain maximum portion of fossil fuels in the energy mix. A consequence of the introduction of these small local boilers into their business was that the portion of fossil fuels was exceeded. Something needed to be done.

Partners

Värnamo Energi AB was formed in 1955 by a merger of two companies. In 1996, when the Swedish electricity market was deregulated, new demands were put on the energy companies to separate the sale of electricity and distribution of electricity (grid), hence the subsidiary Värnamo Elnät (electricity network) was formed. Värnamo Energi AB is partner in two local wind turbines. The operations are divided in business areas: power sale, heat, communication, gas, energy services, electricity grids and wind power. Finnvedsbostäder is the company, owned by the municipality, which originally owned the heat plants.

Activities

Värnamo Energi has been able to finance investments, by support of the national co-financing scheme for investments which will reduce GHG emissions. The innovation voucher was used for compilation of a base for an application to get funding from the scheme. The investments concerned replacement of 14 small boilers with four biofuel boilers in four various communities and expansion / renewal of the grid.

Map of the community of Bor showing the grid extension. Source: Värnamo Energi

SecureChain Partners

Smedjegatan 37
S-352 46 Växjö
Sweden
www.energi kontorsydost.se

University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences
Institute of Waste Management
Muthgasse 107
1109 Vienna, Austria
www.wau.boku.ac.at/abf

Results

The project at Värnamo Energi concerns replacement of 14 small boilers with four biofuel boilers and expansion / renewal of the grid. The boilers are installed in the smaller communities around Värnamo. Some actions have been conducted to attract new customers, since the potential of heat deliveries will increase as a result of the investments. The boilers in "Lanna" and "Bor" has been co-funded with 0,85 MEURO (65 % of total budget). The consultant's report was used as a base for the application for co-funding. The enterprise used the national funding scheme, called "Klimatklivet" (like "The big climate step").

Digging for the extension of the grid in the community of Bor.

Photo: Värnamo Energi

Later on an application for extension of the DH grid in "Bor" was submitted as a consequence of the previously granted one. They were granted for 0.4 MEURO (55 % of total budget). Even later, they submitted a new application for new boilers in "Bredaryd" and "Forsheda". They were granted for 3.0 MEURO (82 % of total budget). They have received even more grants for other actions to decrease fossil fuels in the energy mix, in total 5.1 MEURO.

Comparison of GHG emissions of oil – and wood based district heating systems. Source: BOKU

Progress in the various communities: *Lanna*: Excavations for extension of the DH grid is finalized. The boiler is implemented, it has been test operated and is in regular operation. *Bor*: Excavations is almost finalized. Parts of the equipment to the plant has been delivered. The boiler is ordered, planned to be delivered and operated before the summer of 2018. *Bredaryd*: Excavations are ongoing, almost finalized. The boiler will be delivered before the summer of 2018 and test operated the autumn of this year. *Forsheda*: Excavations will start in May 2018. The boiler will be delivered before the summer of 2018 and test operated the autumn of this year.

Follow-up

The activities with the purpose to attract new customers will go on. According to the conditions in the national funding scheme, the implementation must be carried out before the end of 2018.

Biomass mobilisation through implementation of flue gas condenser

Project partners

Lessebo Fjärrvärme
Stationsgatan 10
S-352 31 Lessebo
Sweden
www.lessebo.se/underwebbar/lessebo-fjarvarme/lessebo-fjarvarme.html

ITK Envifront AB
Blockvägen 8
S-352 45 Växjö
Sweden
www.itk-envifront.se

The essence of the project was to find the most appropriate way to exclude fossil fuel from the energy mix into a heat plant. The feedstock consists of wood biomass, mostly wood chips. Waste heat is brought into the grid of Lessebo from the nearby small pulp mill. The peak – and backup load is secured by bioenergy fuelled combustion facilities in three of these communities. The community of Kosta is the exception, where the deliveries are secured by a fossil liquid gas-fuelled facility. Fossil energy in the energy mix in combination with an expected increased demand of heat from a big customer, were the main driving forces to investigate various options on how to exclude fossil fuel out of the energy mix.

Partners

Lessebo Fjärrvärme is the pilot project coordinator. It is an enterprise, owned by the municipality of Lessebo, located to the southeast part of Sweden. The enterprise is the owner of heat plants which they operate and maintain. The enterprise supplies heat into four various grids in four communities in the municipality of Lessebo. These communities are populated by between 1000 and 3000 inhabitants each, where some of the households, premises and industries have other heating systems, but district heating. ITK Envifront is the supplier of the flue gas condenser.

Activities

It has been a discussion during several years at Lessebo Fjärrvärme on how to exclude the fossil fuel in the energy mix in the heat plant of Kosta. The question became even more relevant when a big customer of the heat announced their plans for expansion of their business, with the consequence of a bigger demand of district heating. The opportunity to take part of the support from the SecureChain project appeared by that time. After taken part of presentations from two consultants, where one of them was hired after a recommendation from one of the other granted SMEs, a decision was made to implement a flue gas condenser. Discussions started with suppliers, one of them a young regional company, ITK Envifront.

SecureChain Partners

Smedjegatan 37
S-352 46 Växjö
Sweden
www.energikontorsydost.se

University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences
Institute of Waste Management
Muthgasse 107
1109 Vienna, Austria
www.wau.boku.ac.at/abf

Results

There will be an investment in a flue gas condenser. This condenser is the first-of-a-kind. The construction is based on a new, innovative technology. An additional value for Lessebo Fjärrvärme is that this novel technology guarantees that the emissions will be lower than the new limits for emissions, which will soon be introduced according to EU legislations.

A new interesting business model has been agreed on for the purchase of the condenser. The rent Lessebo Fjärrvärme will pay during a couple of years is equal to the cost of the fuel they are going to save because of the higher efficiency of the plant in total. The business risk for the SME is minimal, and the supplier is supported by a demonstration plant implemented in the region in which they are operating.

The new EU legislation for emissions from combustion plants in the scale up to 20 MW, affects several of the energy companies in the region. With existing technology, it is primarily a problem to meet the limits of heavy metal emissions. Since the supplier of the condenser guarantees that their new construction meets the new requirements, the SecureChain project enabling the introduction of this technology, is of great value.

Part of the interior of the heat plant in Kosta

Follow-up

The RLP has been in contact with the supplier with the help of Lessebo Fjärrvärme. It has been discussed, that during the upcoming yearly event "The Bioenergy day of Växjö", there will be a focus on novel technologies and best practise in order to enable the heat delivery companies to keep the emissions under the new limits according to new EU-legislations – a seminar where one of the highlights would be this new technology and, if possible after the condenser been

Part of the system for fuel feeding

in operation for a while, to present how the new condenser has affected the efficiency of the plant and the decrease of emissions. Lessebo Fjärrvärme will measure the emissions, probably by the help of students from the Linnaeus University.

Biomass mobilisation through ash recycling

Project partners

Skogsbränsle Småland
Tingsgatan 5
S-362 73 Lenhovda
Sweden
www.skogsbransle.se

XYLEM

Xylem
Jät Petersdal
S-362 52 Jät
Sweden

Figures: Cles Hellqvist and
Askungen Vital

Pilot project concept

The project concept is to accomplish two actions in one, soil preparation and spreading fly ash. The first reason is to make the enterprise less vulnerable by the introduction of a new business, the second reason is to use the argument of securement of the supply of nutrients to the soil in order to get the possibility to purchase branches and tops from forest owners from clear cutting areas. The traditional way to secure the supply of nutrients to the soil is to leave the forest residues on the soil after clear cuttings or final fellings. When the ash is recycled back to forest land, it is normally in the shape of loose ash, which means that brush and vegetation close to the soil get a boost of nutrients. When using granules, the time for the leakage of the nutrients can be decided by choosing a certain radius of the granules.

Partners

Skogsbränsle Småland AB business idea is to purchase, produce and sale of forest fuels, particularly in eastern Småland. The delivered volume is approximately 230 GWh wood fuel distributed as woodchips. Deliveries are made mainly to heating plants where several of them buy all the fuel they need from Skogsbränsle Småland AB. In addition to forest fuels, the company conducts trade with other timber and by-products to a lesser extent. The company also undertakes felling assignments, etc. Forest fuel Småland AB has five employees, three of them work full time. In addition to these five, they employ a number of subcontractors, e.g. forest companies and haulage companies. In its present form and ownership, the company has run since 2009. Xylem is the company of the consultant.

Activities

The consultant compiled a financial model for the investment of granulation equipment. The company has been very active to organise meetings and to take part of seminars on the topic of fly ash. The reason for these discussions is to develop a concept for pelletizing / granulation and spreading, as well as development of business models with ash suppliers.

SecureChain Partners

Smedjegatan 37
S-352 46 Växjö
Sweden
www.energikontorsydost.se

University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences
Institute of Waste Management
Muthgasse 107
1109 Vienna, Austria
www.wau.boku.ac.at/abf

Results

According to the calculations, the plant for granulation has to be in operation 24 days a week and 24 hours a day to be financially viable. It means that the equipment has to be fed with big quantities of fly ash. The big heat plants are located a long distance from each other, meaning that a big part of the ash has to be transported more than 100 km. The costs for transportation are getting higher and they need several long-term agreements with many ash producing companies. The calculations require that the granulation equipment is located to a heat boiler facility, in order to co-finance the technicians required for operation and maintenance. The costs for soil preparation and spreading is lower when they are accomplished at the same moment, in comparison to one by one, but this difference is much lower in comparison to the higher costs for granulation and transportations.

Photo: Johanna Wallin

LCA for various options according to the initiative of Skogsbränsle Småland. Source: BOKU

The new innovative way of granulation and spreading the granules at the same moment as the soil preparation is done, has lower global warming potential in comparison to carry these moments out the traditional way, according to an analysis from BOKU. See figure. In summary the business idea will decrease the carbon dioxide emissions, but on the other hand it is not financially viable.

Follow-up

The costs for transportations, the big number of agreements with ash suppliers and the unforeseen high costs for the granulation equipment entails that the investment is no longer relevant. The topic on how to treat and spread the fly ash to encourage the forest owners to decide for extraction of branches and tops, forest residues, from clear cutting areas will go on in the region, even though this business idea seems to fail.

Improved wood recovery from green wastes

Project partners

AVEA GmbH & Co.KG
Im Eisholz 3
51373 Leverkusen
Germany
www.avea.de

Berthold Häßlin
bh@avea.de

Bergischer
Abfallwirtschaftsverband
Braunswarth 1-3
51766 Engelskirchen
Germany
www.bavweb.de
www.metabolon.de

A communal waste management company improved the process of green waste sorting to make the inadequately utilised wooden fraction of municipal biowaste accessible for thermal utilisation in local incineration plants. The project included a cost-benefit study and a life cycle assessment (LCA) of the enhanced bioenergy chain. The analysis helped to optimise the biowaste sorting logistics, valorise a larger share of the wooden fraction and enhance the biowaste handling capacity from currently 8.000 t/a to a maximum 10.000 t/a by 2018. The pilot project demonstrates how an improved technological process can lead to simultaneous economic and ecological benefits for the company and an increase of biomass mobilisation.

Partners

AVEA is a waste management company and the BAV is a public regional waste association in the Bergisches Land region in NRW, Germany. AVEA's services include collection, transport, treatment and disposal of waste within the area of two counties with an area of 1,300 km² and a population of 550,000 inhabitants. The BAV operates the MSW landfill site Leppe and an innovative educational and research centre, the :metabolon project, to raise public awareness for circular economy, resource efficiency and environmental technology.

Background and objectives

In Germany, circa 50 kg of green waste per inhabitant are collected annually (in NRW circa 44 kg). With further technical optimisation of the green waste collection in the future, circa 75 kg per inhabitant and year is likely to be collected. Under current conditions, this expected volume cannot be composted, because the biomass yards are short of sufficient space. More efficient sorting of the wooden biomass fraction (20-250 mm) is needed. This could increase the volume of recovered wood from green waste to circa 2 million tons per year in Germany, which corresponds to an estimated 24.8 PJ (6.89 TWh) per year equivalent to circa 10% of energy demand in German households.

The novel Circular Economy Act of NRW aims to improve the collection and use of waste, which will result in an increase of biomass streams, including green wastes. The AVEA company planned to enlarge and reorganise the Leppe biomass yard. The objectives were to increase the capacity for the processing of municipal green waste and improve the recovery of wooden biomass, (i) to reduce the external disposal due to capacity shortages, (ii) to improve the sorting of different green waste fractions, and (iii) to recover a calorific valuable fraction as combustible for industrial heating plants.

Green waste, compost heaps and the final compost product

© Pictures by BAV / AVEA

SecureChain partners

University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences
Institute of Waste Management
Muthgasse 107
1109 Vienna, Austria
www.wau.boku.ac.at/abf

Josink Esweg 34
7545 PN Enschede
The Netherlands
www.btgworld.com

Actions and results

The consultations allowed to steer the process to the best result. The exchange with the experts helped essentially to focus the pilot on the main question: How can we optimise the output of solid biomass through an improved sieving process? Following this impulse, AVEA initiated specific sieving tests and carried out detailed cost comparisons of different potential equipment in view of performance, fuel consumption and durability. This allowed to identify a special equipment best suited for the process, a so-called three-fraction sieving machine.

Two scenarios of the sorting process were compared: The first describes the initial setup in which the wooden fraction is extracted after the composting. Here only 0.14 tons of wood or 1.69 GJ/t (0.47 MWh/t) can be retrieved per 1 ton of green waste. In the second scenario (see figure), a larger volume of wood is extracted with improved equipment before the composting. **0.35 tons** of wood or **4.36 GJ/t** (1.21 MWh/t) can be gained per 1 ton of green waste. Note that a smaller amount of compost is produced here, because more wood is recovered. The cost analysis proved the viability of the new process: Although revenues from compost sales decrease, the revenues from recovered wood increase and the external disposal costs can be saved. As a result, the annual processing capacity of the biomass yard can be increased by **+2,000 tons** and the expected total annual revenues can be more than doubled.

Researchers from BOKU carried out a life cycle assessment (LCA) of the two scenarios. Both scenarios result in effective greenhouse gas savings (negative balance), because considerable heat and electricity can be produced from the biomass. However, a significantly larger saving effect is achieved through the new process: the greenhouse gas emissions could be reduced by **203 kg CO₂-equivalents** per ton of green waste (difference status quo-pilot).

State of implementation (May 2018)

The construction works at the site have been almost completed. An additional investment of 100,000 EUR into a new sieve unit and a modernised sieving machine is being realised. The optimised process ensures the continuity of the important contribution of the biomass yard to regional resource efficiency and climate protection.

Biomass mobilisation through landscape element maintenance in Twente

Project partners

Mossendamsdwarweg 1
7472 DB Goor
The Netherlands
www.bruinsenkwest.nl

Mossendamsdwarweg 3
7472 DB Goor
The Netherlands
www.eelerwoude.nl

Pouliestraat 3
7642 EB Wierden
The Netherlands
www.wierden.nl

Pilot project concept

The essence of the project was the selection of the optimal method of maintenance of landscape elements (hedgerows, single-line tree stands, small forests as well as parks and avenues), focusing on Twente. Due to the loss of traditional functions many hedgerows have disappeared and maintenance of remaining ones has been widely neglected in the last decades (see pictures).

With better methods and organisation of the landscape maintenance, costs are expected to come down. Also, proper maintenance will mean that the bushes around the trees can be revitalised, leading to improved biodiversity and a higher quality of the landscape on the one hand (see right-hand picture) and increased biomass mobilisation on the other hand.

Partners

Bruins & Kwast Biomass Management – the pilot project coordinator - is a manufacturer and supplier of secondary (bio-) fuels and raw materials, originating mainly from fresh wood and high-calorific waste streams. Both the fuel and the raw materials are sold across the Benelux, Germany and Poland. Other project partners are a landscape maintenance consulting company (Eelerwoude), a municipality (Wierden), and a landscape management organisation (Landschap Overijssel). These organisations share a vision about the importance of proper landscape element maintenance.

Activities

Activities centred on two main issues 1. To investigate the biomass availability that proper maintenance can yield. 2. Determine the ecological advantages of proper maintenance of landscape elements and other ecosystem services. In addition, the financial implications were determined via an exploitation calculation.

Project partners

Huis "De Horte"
Poppenallee 39
7722 KW Dalfsen
The Netherlands
www.landschapoverijssel.nl

SecureChain Project Partner

Josink Esweg 34
7545 PN Enschede
The Netherlands
www.btgworld.com

University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences
Institute of Waste Management
Muthgasse 107
1109 Vienna, Austria
www.wau.boku.ac.at/abf

Results

The project has yielded an accurate insight in the quantity of hedgerows in Twente. Using satellite images, the total length of the hedgerows in Twente was determined to be roughly 4,000 km (see picture to the right). By comparing this information with the known number of hedgerows that are maintained, it was determined that 80% of all hedgerows in Twente are not properly maintained.

Taking up proper maintenance in Twente would lead to a one-off additional biomass availability of more than 200,000 ton, followed by a sustainable supply of 14,000 tons of biomass per year.

Besides the biomass that can be mobilised through regular maintenance, there are many other advantages. By revitalising the bushes in the hedgerow, local biodiversity increases. Furthermore, a properly maintained hedgerow can act as a dust filter, helps in reducing heat stress and has a positive role in soil fertility and water management. Hedgerows are also of historical value, and are important for an attractive landscape for tourists.

Results of the exploitation calculation showed that costs are higher than the revenues from the sale of biomass. However, if the management is administered by a municipality, or carried out by a collective it is expected that costs can be lowered, so that maintenance can be carried out break-even.

Follow-up

The results of the pilot project have been presented to Groene Metropool Twente. This is a cooperation of several municipalities that aim to develop and improve the countryside in Twente. The presentation was received positively, and as a result a follow-up pilot project is now being developed. The goal of this new project is on the one hand to demonstrate the opportunities of collective maintenance and on the other hand to show the ecological effects of proper maintenance of landscape elements.

Strategic Biomass Storage Facilities Gelderse Vallei

Project partners

RiBo Holding

Krollerweg 11
3774 RG Kootwijkerbroek
The Netherlands

ANV Vallei Horstee
Postbus 33
3790 CA Achterveld
The Netherlands
www.valleiorstee.nl

Gemeente Ede
Bergstraat 4
6711 DD Ede
The Netherlands
www.ede.nl

Pilot project concept

In this project supply of biomass from landscape elements (hedgerows, single-line tree stands, small forests as well as parks and avenues) is combined in a smart manner with biomass supply from common resources (forestry). Aim is to establish a biomass terminal that can produce biomass fuel of different qualities to serve various types of users.

By storing biomass in combination with drying and sieving a regular supply of biomass is ensured. High quality wood chips with a defined moisture content and morphology can thus be supplied to smaller boilers, while lower quality fractions can be supplied to larger boilers that are more robust and can handle lower quality biomass. The pilot project was initiated based on an ongoing effort to stimulate the maintenance of landscape elements in the Gelderse Vallei.

Partners

The company Ribo Holding – the pilot project initiator – is located in the Gelderse Vallei at the location of a former animal fodder company. Other partners in the project were Borgman Beheer Advies, expert in setting up biomass fuel supply chains. Supply of the biomass and organisation of the landscape maintenance activities was carried out by the association ANV Vallei Horstee. The municipalities of Ede and Barneveld supported the pilot project.

Project partners

Raadhuisplein 2
3771 ER Barneveld
The Netherlands
www.barneveld.nl

Dreijenlaan 2
6703 HA Wageningen
The Netherlands
www.borgmanbeheer.nl

SecureChain Project Partner

Josink Esweg 34
7545 PN Enschede
The Netherlands
www.btgworld.com

Activities

The project started analysing the siting and design of the strategic storage facilities, applying lessons learned from visiting and inspecting similar facilities. An investment and operational plan for the initial phase was developed, as well as a scaling-up plan and an exploitation calculation, that consider future capacity expansion, in line with the anticipated growing availability of wood chips.

Results

The operational and investment plan was developed, describing the activities to be carried out and the required investments. Although use could be made of facilities already in place at the former animal fodder plant (like a weighing bridge), several investments/infrastructural requirements were identified, such as a retaining wall to be able to store and load wood chips at the terrain, a tarpaulin (see picture) that would allow for moisture reduction in the stored wood chips while keeping the rain out; a shovel/loader for occasional use, and a monitoring system to control the intake and supply of wood chips.

The space available for wood chips storage is 3,500 m³, which is sufficient for the first phase. There is enough additional space available on the terrain for scaling-up to about 5,000 tonne/year.

Besides determining the required investment, exploitation calculations were made. An amount of 1,200 tonne/year was calculated as the break-even point. Above this amount, the costs for intake, handing, sieving and supply of wood chips would be compensated by the higher income because of higher wood chips quality and associated prices.

Follow-up

At the moment the storage space is in use, but faces challenges acquiring enough biomass. This is on the one hand a problem of lack of local supply, and on the other hand caused by increased competition from other market players. Priority is given to intensify actions to increase the wood supply before making a decision about new investments.

Innovative biomass harvesting machine for top- and branch wood

Project partners

Buurtweg 42
6971 KM Oeken (Brummen)
The Netherlands
www.hissink-oeken.nl

Zilverlinde 24b
7131 MN Lichtenvoorde
The Netherlands
www.inodes.nl

Pilot project concept

In the Netherlands, a high population density and a fairly limited forest cover (11% of the land area) mean it's important to consider a range of biomass feedstocks for renewable energy production. An untapped potential of woody biomass from forests and landscape elements is the top- and branch wood that becomes available as a result of forest and landscape maintenance.

For the process to be economically viable and considering the small average plot size in the Netherlands, it is important that top- and branch wood can be removed in a low-cost, efficient way. In this pilot project a machine was developed that can harvest, chip and transport top- and branch wood in a single pass. This avoids the use of separate cranes and forwarders.

Partners

Hissink & Zonen is an all-round mechanization company, located in Oeken (Gelderland/NL). Hissink has evolved from an agricultural mechanization company to a supplier and developer of tractors and machinery for landscaping, forestry and agriculture, including specialised machinery for biomass harvesting, collection and logistics.

Activities

With support of the engineering company iNodes a design was made for the new single-pass machine. In several iterations a collection unit was engineered that would be able to collect top- and branch wood, and to transport this material to a chipper. This collection unit was designed to be able to operate on relatively uneven ground.

SecureChain Partners

Josink Esweg 34
7545 PN Enschede
The Netherlands
www.btgworld.com

University of Natural
Resources and Life Sciences
Institute of Waste
Management
Muthgasse 107
1109 Vienna, Austria
www.wau.boku.ac.at/abf

Next, a prototype was built and tested; first in-house, and later on in an actual forest stand. Applying life-cycle assessment (LCA) SecureChain partner BOKU (Vienna) studied the environmental advantages of using the machine as compared to the current practice. An exploitation calculation was made to determine the viability of investing in further development of the machine.

Results

The prototype machine was constructed in 2016/2017 at the facilities of Hissink (see picture). Use was made of an existing mobile chipper, and the collection device was constructed and mounted up-front. In-house testing showed that the machine functioned well, and basic functions (movement, raising and lowering of the collector unit, chipping, emptying the chips storage container) could be performed without problems.

After the in-house test, the machine was field tested in the estate “De Treek” in the Netherlands (see picture). During the field test it appeared that the machine was not working optimal yet, and that further developments were required. In addition, the weight of the machine (10 tonnes) appeared rather high in light of its intended application. This can be problematic on sensitive forest soils.

The LCA study of BOKU showed positive results in terms of CO₂-eq emissions when the machine is compared to the alternatives. The exploitation calculation indicated that the development of this machine could be financially attractive.

Follow-up

The additional developments required to make the machine ready for the market will mean that extra investments in R&D are needed. Funding for this is being sought.

Growing the production of modern solid biofuels for small-scale heaters

Project partners

C/ Abres del papa, 14
08787 La Pobla de
Claramunt (Barcelona)
Spain
www.grouprenerbio.com/ca/

Pilot project concept

The essence of the project is to scale up the production capacity of a Pellet Manufacturing Plant up to 64.000 tn/year. The company undertake an economic feasibility study to measure economies of scale and support fund raising activities.

In parallel, the SME visits referent pellet mills in Austria that helps to design the pellet mill scale-up project. Project partners help the company to certifies their pellets with Dinplus quality certification.

Secure Chain has been also useful to define the vision of the company. The company managers commit to eliminate CO₂ Emissions from electricity generation operations. Thanks to the Life Cycle Assessment, managers raise concern to measure and mitigate the CO₂ food print from all the company's operations.

Partners

Grup Renerbio is a family owned and managed business with more than 20 years' experience in energy generation, forestry management and energy services. The group consists of three business units. Energy Generation and OMIE Wholesale Electric Market Commercialization. Commercialization of heat and power targeting Small Medium Enterprises. Pellet manufacturer certified as Enplus A1 Premium and Dinplus.

SecureChain partners

Forest Science and Technology
Centre of Catalonia
Ctra. de St. Llorenç de Morunys
a Port del Comte, km 2
25280 Solsona
www.ctfc.cat/en

UPC – Universitat Politècnica de
Catalunya Campus
Diagonal Sud, Edifici PI
(Pavelló I). Av. Diagonal, 647
08028 Barcelona
Spain
www.upc.edu

University of Natural Resources
and Life Sciences
Institute of Waste Management
Muthgasse 107
1109 Vienna, Austria
www.wau.boku.ac.at/abf

Activities

Activities centred on three main issues: 1. Financial forecasting and Risk Assessment to support production scale-up benefits, 2. Life Cycle Assessment to measure the CO₂ food print from all the company's operations, 3. Product Quality Assurance and certification.

Results

The economic analysis and companies financials forecasting has been used to secure debt funding from Regional Banks.

The Finance Director assistance to Climate Bond Initiative 2017 Annual Conference in London was useful to meet project finance investors. The company introduced their activities and presented a new project consisting on a Biomass CHP plant in Catalonia.

The Head of Production participation in a Pellet Mill visit in Austria was useful to decide the best manner to scale-up production.

The company it is been also favoured with the capacitation on quality assurance and the Din plus certification of their product.

Follow up

The company did not reach yet a production of 64.000 tn/year so is still in the process to consolidate the scale-up process.

It is an interesting case to follow to understand how competitive is the pellet produced in south Europe to replace central-European imports and from overseas.

Biomass distribution to end consumers with an innovative logistics model

Project partners

Crta. Palamós, 85
17460 Celrà
Catalonia (Spain)
www.salaforestal.com

Pilot project concept

The essence of the project is to reduce transport costs when distributing biomass to small scale woodchip boilers. The company undertake a feasibility study to test new processes and equipment's. The ultimate goal is to commercially implement an automatic and remote-controlled solid biofuels dispenser for distribution optimisation.

The pilot project happens in Catalonia and aims to serve clients located nearby, around 200 Km, the woodchip plant. Nowadays, these clients are served with a single stage logistics model that carries expensive distribution costs. This new model allows to attend unserved clients that currently face prohibitive transport costs to turn into biomass.

The project brings new technologies such as RFID, prediction systems and Internet-of-Things to traditional and environmental-friendly business to boost sustainable energies.

Partners

Sala Forestal – the pilot project coordinator - is a forest operator and manufacturer and supplier of secondary (bio-) fuels and raw materials, originating mainly from their own forest operations. Both the fuel and the raw materials are marketed in a sustainable and professional manner in Spain and France. Other partners are the Catalan Agriculture Authority that granted and recognized the project as an innovative solution to spur bioenergy in the energy.

Activities

Activities centred on three main issues 1. Estimate savings in transport cost and CO2 emissions with the new logistics model 2. Prototype machinery, equipment's and processes required to deploy the innovative logistics model. 3. Identify the best localization in Catalonia to deploy the first new logistics model.

SecureChain partners

Forest Science and Technology
Centre of Catalonia
Ctra. de St. Llorenç de Morunys
a Port del Comte, km 2
25280 Solsona
www.ctfc.cat/en

UPC – Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya Campus Diagonal Sud, Edifici PI (Pavelló I). Av. Diagonal, 647 08028 Barcelona Spain
www.upc.edu

University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences
Institute of Waste Management
Muthgasse 107
1109 Vienna, Austria
www.wau.boku.ac.at/abf

Results

The project has yielded an accurate insight in the quantity of woodchip that can be mobilized when the new logistics model is applied. The project developed economic analysis models that size the investments required to deploy the new technology and proof economic returns to the company.

The economic analysis conclude that the proposed logistics model would cut transport costs up to 30% and reduce CO2 emissions between 20 - 40% compared with the current distribution model.

The project accelerates the technology development and step-up company's confidence to pursue the business opportunity. Secure chain activities were helpful to decide how to protect the technology, better communicate the value proposition and identify the right partners to make it happen.

Figure: Example for the calculation of transport emissions

Follow-up

The company aims to build a commercial prototype in 2019 and validate expected benefits in a commercial environment. The company pretends to fully deploy the innovative logistics model in 2020.

This case study shows how crucial is transport cost to make biomass competitive. Investments on transnational biomass transport infrastructures are required to compete with fossil fuels that count with favourable transports costs due to transnational transport infrastructures such us LNG Pipelines.

Small-scale CHP for autarky farms

Project partners

Taarapõllu Talu OÜ
Kangsti, Varstu Vald
66103 Võrumaa
Estonia
www.taarapollu.ee

Märja Monte OÜ
Vee 1
1406 Tartu maakond
Estonia
www.monte.ee

The aim of this project was to research the opportunities and effects to replace fossil fuel boiler of the farm with a biomass CHP. Specifically, the farm intends to install a wood gasification CHP. CHP suitable for the farm has capacity of 45kW electric and 120 kW heat. It is not common to install CHP plants in Estonia, despite that these solutions can be viable for numerous companies in Estonia. Therefore, introducing these technological solutions and best practices of working plants is innovative for local companies. In the case of economic profitability, the market is open towards implementing technology.

Partners

Taarapõllu farm is officially certificated organic farm that grows berries, fruits and vegetables in Võru County hills. Tartu Regional Energy Agency (TREA) has best competence and cooperation abilities in renewable energy solutions and energy efficiency in South-Estonia. TREA hired external consultant Pavel Bogdanov from Märja Monte OÜ for pre-study of technical solutions and profitability calculations. Märja Monte have had over 40 years of experience in thermal energy sector and P. Bogdanov has been in lead of that company from the beginning.

Background and objectives

Farm has an organic processing recognition, they products are marked and sold with eco-label, therefore is important to use as much as possible renewable energy to cover energy demand for production process. Farm leaders are interested of these solutions that are energy efficient, environmental friendly and that work at the local wood or other renewable energy sources. Pre-study of project addresses the following energy technologies as development scenarios: the local boiler plant wood working on woodchips for heat supply (Scenario I), woodchips-based boiler plant with local heating grid connecting all premises (Scenario II) and combined heat and power (CHP) plant running on woodchips (Scenario III). Company's heating and electricity consumption volumes were calculated based on forecast seen on Company's development plans. Calculated annual energy demand is 340 MWh of electricity and 625 MWh heat energy. Today they use light oil for heat production, by company's development forecast they will need 62 tons of oil.

Choice of Taarapõllu products

© Pictures by cooppank.ee, Pixabay.com, Taarapõllu, Astri.ee, Looduspere.ee

SecureChain partner

Tartu Regional Energy Agency
Narva mnt 3
51009 Tartu
Estonia
www.trea.ee

Actions and results

In the framework of the project meeting in Estonia international experts visited Taarapõllu farm in January 2018 and there was discussion how to use Life Cycle Analysis to market Taarapõllu's eco-label products even better. Project team hired external expert by using of SecureChain IV for making of pre-feasibility study for biomass-based energy system for Farm. Suitable CHP plant for the farm was selected by considering heat demand. Three different scenarios were studied and compared if investment is made with and without national grant of 50%. The investment was evaluated by simple payback time, Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and Net-Present Value (NPV) that was calculated for 15 years – minimum lifespan of new boiler. Cash flow and the profitability analysis has demonstrated that from the three energy supply alternatives are equally profitable two: wood chips-based boiler and construction of cogeneration plants. For all scenarios a simple payback period was from approximately 3,5 years (with financial support of 50%) to 8 years (without of financial support).

Figure: Alternative simple payback times in years and self-financing volume for different scenarios

CHP scenario has equally good payback period compared with other plants, but initial investment would be about 2 times higher than other technologies and increased requirements for fuel quality and is somewhat more complicated to operate. Wood chips fired boiler is a simple technology that does not require a very high-quality fuel and is well-established practice. Project calculated impact on CO₂ emissions reduction is 485 tCO₂ per year and over 4000 GJ renewable energy produced annually if CHP plant is installed.

State of implementation (May 2018)

Despite the fact that actions were stopped for while in Taarapõllu because of management and ownership changes in progress and previously planned national grants are not open yet, Taarapõllu is still looking to involve investments. Next meeting with investors will held on June 2018.s

Small-scale CHP wood gasifier for village cooperative (Cooperative Ilmasaare)

Project partners

Haldusühistu Ilmasaare MTÜ
Ilmasaare, Lääne-Harju vald,
76703 Harju maakond
Estonia
www.ilmasaare.ee

Project relates to one of the stage of development of energy cooperative, which is planning to become an independent community and independent form energy grids on next 10-15 years. There are 4-6 single-family homes under construction in the village and for the future it is planned up to 55 sites for construction. Project is focused on energy supply for Ilmasaare village and woody biomass transformation to energy through combined heat and power (CHP) unit based on wood gasifier technology. Energy needs for first stage can be solved by electrical capacity of 45 kW and 110 kW for heat. In future households will install PV-panels and cooperative solar park will be developed for electricity production. Supply chain covers stockpiling necessary materials for CHP unit installation (equipment, technology, woodchips and byproducts of forest industry) and selling of produced energy to villagers and enterprises located in the area.

Partners

Commercial Association Ilmasaare is a commercial cooperative and the whole of its activity is based on the cooperative business. The main activity of the "self-financed" village Ilmasaare is the administrative and economic arrangements of village. Researcher from Tallinn University of Technology, Ülo Kask, prepared a preliminary study for independent energy supply and investment project. Tartu Regional Energy Agency is consulting Ilmasaare Village.

Background and objectives

Ilmasaare eco-community is interested of energy solutions that are energy efficient, minimally polluting the environment, and that work at the local wood or other renewable sources of energy and/or local. Ilmasaare is evolving self-sufficient eco-village and in the future energy cooperation that is independent from grid. Administrative association of Ilmasaare was founded in 2014. It is in North-Estonia, 45 km away from Tallinn, the capital of Estonia. Two years earlier, in 2012 NGO Ilmasaare Society was founded for the purpose to develop local villages economy, social life and culture and advocating green stances to save nature. Co-operative goal for Ilmasaare is to organize all

The vision of Ilmasaare eco-village

© Pictures by Ilmasaare

SecureChain partners

Tartu Regional Energy Agency
Narva mnt 3
51009 Tartu
Estonia
www.trea.ee

the village's energy supply and management, both for households and for business purposes. Ilmasaare village economy and energy independence is based on sawmill that residues can be used to produce electricity and heat for village's households. The plans foresee the next 10-15 years of Ilmasaare village development. There are up to 55 households planned to build into Ilmasaare village with average 150 m² of heated space per house that consumes annually around 13 MWh of energy.

Actions and results

Co-operative goal is to organize all of the village's energy supply and management, both for households and for business purposes. For this, they are planning to set up in 2017 a new legal body, an energy cooperative NGO "Ilmasaare Energy", whose principal activity is the production of electricity and heat in cogeneration plants. The heat-and electricity cogeneration will based on wood-fuel pyrolysis.

On the recommendation of the management of the village the study addresses on the three alternatives- solar energy generation with PV panels, micro station of combined heat and power generation and micro power plant working for wood-gas. In the study was evaluated profitability of three alternatives. The cost-benefit also sensibility and risk analysis were made. In terms of cash flow, and a sensitivity analysis has shown that from the three alternative electricity generation the using of solar PV panels is the most profitable. But as village needs also heat energy, the calculations showed if heat demand will rise to 420 MWh the micro CHP will become profitable also. An option is also power generation station running on wood-gas without producing heat energy. Payback time was 16 years, but it is more stable on production and security of supply of electrical energy then PV panels.

In result of study and knowledge gained the village cooperative need to move forward for developing the concept of village. Several meetings was held in this reporting period with topic of updating the concept of village and they energy management and to find possible investors for CHP plant. Also, meetings was targeted to prepare the roadshow. TREA proposed different options, three –steps roadshow, for community to find resources for investment on CHP plant. First step was looking for opportunities in national grant schemas. There is no available national grants for planned actions. Second step was - visiting of local banks for business loan possibilities, getting familiar with conditions and ask for proposal from banks. Representatives of village visited banks and checked possibilities for bank loan. There is option to use bank loan for financing of CHP. Third step was to arrange, with help of RLP (TREA), one-to- one meeting with possible investors. Meetings with TREA and two energy companies was organized for discuss of one to one meeting when village is ready to introduce their pilot.

State of implementation (May 2018)

There are no investors who would be willing to invest in the project and previously planned use of national grants didn't happen because grants are not open yet.

More bark for biofuel, more wood for MDF!

Project partner

ALFA Wood Group
7km Grevena-Mavranaioi
GR 511 00, Grevena
Greece
www.alfawood.gr

Pilot project concept

The project addresses the use of bark for energy production, which nowadays in the Western Macedonia region of Greece is not used at all. Bark is rather left in the forest and can even become a negative factor, in case of wild fires. Bark contains however a high calorific value and could significantly increase the biomass input for biomass power plants.

ALFA Wood Pindos S.A. is a well-established wood panel producer. They aim to ensure the necessary quantities of raw materials to cover the needs of the daily operation of the plant: currently the main supply is from the domestic residues market and covers 100% of the plant needs in heat production.

The company has installed two boilers of diathermic oil with combustion of biomass, designed to produce heat of 14.000.000 kcal / h with oil temperature of 275°C. The daily requirements of biomass fuel amount to 120-130 tons in total. The main fuels are husks and wood chips derived from the subproducts of the production process (logs peeling, mechanical separation of wood particles etc.).

The main concept is therefore the exploitation of the left over bark in forest operations as a new supply for thermal energy production in the existing plant. This demands a re-organisation of the supply chain, in order to include bark in its load capacity, the re-formation of suppliers to identify and store this raw material, the re-structuring of the production site of the company to be able to store, chip and feed the bark in the boilers.

In this sense, the advisory support of the mentoring package was expected to be used exactly to achieve these targets: with the assistance of the external consultant, the company will put an effort to re-organise its supply chain by means of contacting actors and stakeholders and help them communicate the needs to identify and store the raw material, re-structure its production site for the new storage and feeding needs.

SecureChain Project Partners

ZEP Area
GR 50100, Kozani
Greece
www.clube.gr

Centre for Research and
Technology Hellas
Institute for Energy Resources
Management (CPERI)
P.O. Box 95
GR 50200, Ptolemaida
Greece
www.lignite.gr

University of Natural Resources
and Life Sciences
Institute of Waste Management
Muthgasse 107
1109 Vienna, Austria
www.wau.boku.ac.at/abf

Partners

The ALFA Wood group is the pilot project leader, represented by the owners, Mr. Anthony and Chris Adamopoulos. The external consultant of the company is Dr. George Ntalos. His main task was to re-organise the company's supply chain by communicating the concept to the actors and stakeholders in the supply chain, and target the needs to identify and store the raw material, and re-structure the production site for the new storage needs.

Results

According to the new business plan, Alfa Wood examined the possibility to substitute part of the energy wood, which is currently used as biofuel in the company's biomass boilers, with bark from the logs that the company uses to produce its main product (MDF).

Alfa Wood conducted a series of analyses of various percentages of bark within the fuel mixture, from a 80% bark to 100% bark. The laboratory analyses, carried out with support from CERTH/CPERI, demonstrated that it is feasible to substitute for a great part, even entirely, the useful wood with bark, the latter having a high calorific value and therefore acting sufficiently as a biomass fuel.

With the assistance of the SecureChain partners CLUBE, CERTH, BOKU and UPC, further feasibility calculations of such a substitution were performed. The results are encouraging as the economic benefits seem to follow the increase of the rate of substitution, without any further losses in technical or other dimensions of the operation of the company. Alfa Wood has however to pay attention how to best re-organise both its feedstock storage facilities and its supply chain: the various inflows and their combination need to be clearly separated and optimised in order to improve both the quality of its MDF products and the production of thermal energy for its needs.

Additionally, two further issues have been examined: The provision of the bark as a raw material is necessarily related to the operation of the forest owner cooperatives, which, following a new relevant law that forces them to merge, is expected to change the wood market in Greece. The company will follow closely this drastic change, to communicate with the new organisational schemes that will emerge and assist their mentoring and coaching, in order to secure standard quantities and qualities of wood supply.

At the same time, the company will also look into alternative biomass suppliers to ensure its supply in this context. Contacts with other companies in the SecureChain project (AZ Bioenergeia) generated potential mutual interest in developing energy crops. Finally, ALFA Wood also has shown interest in participation in a potential solution to establish a District Heating network for the nearby town of Grevena.

Fast-growing biomass plantations for bioenergy end users

Project partner

βιοενέργεια

AZ Bioenergia
Παπαϊορδανίδης Α.
Ευαγγέλου Σ. και ΣΙΑ Ο.Ε.
5ο Χιλιόμετρο Κοζάνης -
Πτολεμαΐδας, Τ.Θ.:95, Κοζάνη
501 00

www.facebook.com/AZbioenergeia/

Pilot project concept

The project aims to develop electricity and thermal energy production from biomass. In the long term, the project includes the installation and operation of a power plant that will operate based on biomass. The total installed power for this plant will be 2.5 MWe and 7.5 MWth. The electrical side of this power plant/station will connect and provide supply to the National Greek Network of Transmission and Distribution of Electricity. The thermal energy can be used to cover heating needs locally (district heating). Due to its rural location and the adjacent activities, scenarios envisage the supply of the biomass materials from adjacent greenhouses and fast-growing plantations to significantly reducing the operating costs.

The biomass needs for the venture can be supplied from the agricultural sector, food industry and wood processing industries of the region of Western Macedonia in Greece. The biomass material will be collected from the local producers and processed accordingly. This is a crucial point for the success of the operation as it ensures the smooth flow of production and simultaneously engaging two major parts, creating a new supply and production chain.

AZ Bioenergia has already signed contracts with farmers in the region for harvesting of their production for biomass purposes. In addition, AZ Bioenergia experimented with the cultivation of paulownia for biomass in an area of 0.6 ha (580 trees) within the vicinity of the proposed power plant location.

Partners

AZ Bioenergia selected the company KOEM Consulting as an external consultant, who supported the preparation and the evaluation of potential investment proposals. In addition, it examined the model of logistics and supply chain management. Specifically, the research proposed solutions and guidance for network configuration, distribution strategy, and inventory management.

SecureChain Project Partners

ZEP Area
GR 50100, Kozani
Greece
www.clube.gr

Centre for Research and
Technology Hellas
Institute for Energy Resources
Management (CPERI)
P.O. Box 95
GR 50200, Ptolemaida
Greece
www.lignite.gr

University of Natural Resources
and Life Sciences
Institute of Waste Management
Muthgasse 107
1109 Vienna, Austria
www.wau.boku.ac.at/abf

Results

In 2013, AZ formed a pilot greenhouse in order to cultivate and experiment with Paulownia plants, a fast-growing biomass crop. Later in 2013, the seedlings were transplanted from the greenhouse into the field. Since then, the company is monitoring their development with regular measurements.

So far the results are encouraging regarding the first 3 years of growth (2014-2017). The goal for 2018 is to create a larger scale greenhouse in order to produce larger numbers of seedling plants for energy purposes. AZ expects to undertake first harvest trials by December 2018.

The power plant implementation will be placed on land section registry 169 at Alonakia of Kozani Municipality, on a total surface area of 2.44 hectares. Licenses have been obtained from the Regulatory Authority for Energy (RAE) and the associated environmental authorities of the region of Western Macedonia, while the connection specifications of the Transmission Greek Electricity Distribution Network (DEDIE) and the installation license are in the pipeline and expected to be delivered.

However, there are significant delays in this venture, which raise concerns about the feasibility of the investment concerning the power plant construction. During the project, the discussions with the SecureChain partners and foreign experts from BOKU and UPC have made substantial contribution towards re-examining the whole business model.

At the same time, an opportunity has appeared due to the imminent closure of the Lignite Power Plant of Amyndeo that also provides thermal energy to the District Heating network of the town of Amyndeo. The power loss is going to be substituted by a biomass plant of 30MW, which requires substantial biomass quantities from the regional market. In this context, the AZ company is keen to seizing the opportunity and examines the upscaling of the Paulownia plantations, either through their own production, or through the production of farmers under AZ guidance.

A follow-up activity of coaching and assistance of technical and logistical solutions and technical support from the Regional Lead Partner is foreseen after the end of SecureChain. This includes support towards identifying potential funding, expanding the networking and developing the business case.

Improving the Biogas Supply Management in a local biogas in Kozani

Project partners

Matesion Ltd.
Kastorias 1
GR 50100, Kozani
Greece
www.matesion.gr

Join4CS

Foundation for the
Interregional Co-operation,
the Co-creation, the Collective
and the Constitution of our
Common Future
Perdika 16, 50100 Kozani
Greece

Pilot project concept

The project addresses efforts to establish a well-structured biogas supply chain that could better address the feedstock needs of biogas plants in the region of Western Macedonia, Greece. The second goal was to better handle the animal manure in order to increase its added value, instead of burning the useful agricultural biomass residues. Biogas use is common all over the regional authority. The pilot project focussed on the Kozani district where Matesion Ltd. has established its biogas plant.

At the beginning of its operation, Matesion used to rely on animal waste from mink breeding farms existing in the area as its main feedstock material. In addition, they accepted different feedstock (fruits, vegetables, animal manure, fat from food processing companies etc.) with strong seasonal character. The diverse feedstock material and the continuous changes in the mixture in the fermenter led to poor biogas production and problems with handling and insertion of this feedstock material.

A radical improvement to the quality and quantity of biogas was possible by adopting a different strategy in supply chain management. The change was a result of the support by the SecureChain project, through the advice provided by the Regional Lead Partner and the international partners involved.

The new strategy shifted to different feedstock material with more stable character throughout the year. Instead of using mink animal manure as a primary feedstock material with problems in seasonality and the quality of material (usually came along with impurities and stones), Matesion now receives clean manure from a poultry farm in its vicinity. In addition, the company established a contract with a vegetable oil refinery that supplies them with vegetable oil waste which is appropriate for biogas production and a good biogas yield. Another important supplier is the food industry that was looking for a way to rid-off the 'end of life' food material; Matesion could provide them with the adequate solution.

SecureChain Project Partners

ZEP Area
GR 50100, Kozani
Greece
www.clube.gr

P.O. Box 95
GR 50200, Ptolemaida
Greece
www.lignite.gr

Partners

Matesion, as the pilot project owner, has planned, developed and operated the pilot biogas plant in the district area of Kozani. Join4Cs is a non-profit company that strives to promote innovation practices in energy and environmental sectors. They supported Matesion Ltd, in their effort to advance their supply chain in order i) to increase efficiency and proper waste management. (ii) to improve the sorting of different green waste fractions, and (iii) to recover a calorific valuable fraction as combustible for industrial heating plants. Furthermore two civil engineers, the company Grigoriadis and Sofologis Ltd., was involved in the collaboration.

Results

According to the business plan, Matesion Ltd. had to improve the substrate in order to increase the biogas yield. The company had to use specific substrates in a controlled combination in order to eliminate the 'death' period in feedstock supply, as well as to improve the quality of the substrate and its homogenization.

This was achieved through a change of the substrate mix which improved the C:N ratio and allowed to obtain a more homogenized substrate with a standard combination of different feedstock. Following this new procedure, the company manages to keep constant feedstock characteristics and reduce losing time period needed for the homogenization of the new substrate. This is a result of the identification of new feedstock, such as the vegetable oil from an oil refinery, and the expired food waste from the dairy food industry. The new feedstock has very good biogas potential and, most importantly, is available in standard quantities and in regular supplies. The company increased the operational time and significantly reduced the down time between different waste batches, improving the biogas yield and reducing the volume of post-treatment material.

In numbers, the new combination of feedstock improved the biogas yield by approximately 20% and at the same time reduced the down periods by almost 40%. As a consequence, the capacity factor of the biogas unit increased from 5,500 to 7,500 hours/year. The overall energy production was increased reaching the 3,000 GJ/year or 830 MWh/year. This also improved the financial performance of the unit by around 20%.

Pellet production vs distribution, and full customer service (ESCO model)

Project partners

Plaça Catalunya 6
08140 - Caldes De Montbui
Barcelona – Catalonia

<http://www.probiomassa.com>

Pilot project concept

The goal of this pilot project was to scale up their current pellet distribution business, in both ways of the bioenergy supply chain:

- Upstream: by opening either a pellet/woodchip manufacturing line or diversifying the pellet/woodchip wholesale supplier's portfolio. In either case, wood would be sourced from local forests where arrangements with forest owners have been reached.
- Downstream: by selling boilers and stoves together with pellets and woodchips, or even by selling final energy (heat, electricity) under an ESCO scheme

The pilot project is based in the PROBIOMASSA logistic facilities located in the town of Caldes de Montbui, at about 20km from Barcelona. Pellet clients are distributed among the counties of Bages, Vallès Oriental and Vallès Occidental, and pellets are supplied in bulk (with a pneumatic, adapted truck that can fill the final client tank), in big bags (up to 1000kg) or in small bags (15 kg).

The key aspect to analyse was the viability of a pellet manufacturing plant, and the financing options that could make it possible.

Partners

Probiomassa is part of the Electra Caldense (l'Electra) group, led by a utility company located in the Vallès region, with headquarters in Caldes de Montbui. The company is dedicated to the design, construction and operation of energy infrastructures and has 101 years of history. The utility supplies electricity to 14,000 clients. The business maturation drove to diversify its energy sources and nowadays complements electricity supply with gas and solid biomass supply.

SecureChain Project Partner

Forest Science and Technology
Centre of Catalonia
Ctra. de St. Llorenç de Morunys
a Port del Comte, km 2
25280 Solsona
www.ctfc.cat/en

UPC – Universitat Politècnica de
Catalunya Campus
Diagonal Sud, Edifici PI
(Pavelló I). Av. Diagonal, 647
08028 Barcelona
Spain
www.upc.edu

Nowadays Electra Caldense also operates as an Energy Service Company (ESCO); Electra facilitates the upfront investment, the O&M and supplies the fuel to the client that gets all he needs solved without assuming an initial investment and just compromising a recurrent affordable fee.

Probiomassa was founded in 2012 and currently has 3 employees, with a turnover of about € 200,000 and biomass sales of 1200Tn per year.

Activities

The evolution of this project primarily depended on the decision to be adopted with respect to installing an own pellet manufacturing plant vs scaling up the pellet wholesale procurement operations.

Results

The project partners developed an operational costs model that has been key to characterise the minimum level of biomass sales that would be needed to make the pellet manufacturing plant viable; after several months of sales growth monitoring, PROBIOMASSA could conclude that such minimum levels could not be reached in the medium term, and hence the construction of the plant was discarded.

The project then focused on diversifying the pellet wholesale suppliers' portfolio, with emphasis on local (small) manufacturers with limited distribution capacity. As a result, a new pellet distribution hub business model has been initiated by which several pellet brands are commercialised by the PROBIOMASSA sales network. The company has also increased its wood chip sales by optimising and scaling up its distribution vehicle fleet.

And this strategy has proved to be extremely convenient, because it enabled PROBIOMASSA to withstand one large pellet manufacturer bankruptcy that took place right in the middle of this last winter campaign.

In parallel, the project has strengthened the company's sales by securing new industrial customers, such as a woodchip supply contract signed in 2017 with the Termosolar Borges power plant, as well as a strategic partnership alliance with one of the largest Catalan Engineering and Civil Works firm.

The constitution of the Biomass Cluster of Catalonia and its active role awarded to Probiomassa as member of the board since 2016 is considered of great value to enhance the company visibility, networking and regulatory outreach in the coming years.

Probiomassa was the company that received the most business meeting requests at the SecureChain B2B side event held at the Catalan Biomass Fair in February 2017.

Follow-up

The company aims to continue its techno-economic operational optimisation by engaging in medium to large ESCO projects (such as district heating and cooling networks).

More information: www.securechain.eu

Main authors: Uwe Kies, Patrick Reumerman (BTG)

Contributors: John Vos (BTG), Pol Arranz, Frederic Horta (UPC), Göran Gustavsson (ESS), Gudrun Obersteiner, Silvia Scherhauser (BOKU), Yannis Fallas, Nikos Ntabos (CLUBE), Martin Kikas (TREA), Marco Pagels (DINCERTCO), Valantis Ketikidis (CERTH), Pere Navarro (CTFC)

Date: June 2018

Publisher: BTG Biomass Technology Group BV
Josink Esweg 34, 7545 PN Enschede
The Netherlands
+31 (0)53 486 1186
office@btgworld.com
www.btgworld.com

Funding support: European Commission Horizon 2020
Research and Innovation Programme
Grant agreement no. 646457
01/04/2015 – 31/07/2018
www.securechain.eu

SecureChain

sustainable biomass energy

Consortium

BTG – Biomass Technology Group BV
Enschede, The Netherlands | www.btgworld.com

UPC – Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya
Institute of Sustainability and Department of Business Management | Barcelona, Spain | <http://is.upc.edu>

ESS – Energikontor Sydost AB
Växjö, Sweden | www.energikontorsydost.se

BOKU – University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences
Institute of Waste Management
Vienna, Austria | www.wau.boku.ac.at/abf.html

CLUBE – Cluster of Bioenergy & Environment of Western Macedonia
Kozani, Greece | www.clube.gr

TREA – Tartu Regional Energy Agency MTÜ
Tartu, Estonia | www.trea.ee

DINCERTCO Gesellschaft für Konformitätsbewertung mbH
Berlin, Germany | www.dincertco.de

CBI – Climate Bonds Initiative
London, United Kingdom | www.climatebonds.net

CERTH / CPERI – Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, Chemical Process and Energy Resources Institute
Thessaloniki, Greece | www.isfta.gr

CTFC – Centre Tecnològic Forestal de Catalunya
Solsona, Spain | www.ctfc.cat

Funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement no. 646457 from 01/04/2015 – 31/07/2018
www.securechain.eu